

1 **Large-scale Seismic Risk Assessment Integrating**
2 **Nonlinear Soil Behavior and Soil-Structure**
3 **Interaction Effects**

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7 **Abstract** The need for an accurate risk assessment procedure led to the de-
8 velopment of various fragility and vulnerability curves, covering a wide range
9 of building typologies. Nonlinear soil behavior and soil-structure interaction
10 (SSI) effects play an essential role in this outcome; nevertheless, their influence
11 is usually neglected. While for building-specific applications, these effects may
12 be explicitly considered, it is currently impossible to account for such effects
13 in large-scale seismic risk analyses. We examine the effectiveness of a broad set
14 of fragility modifiers (FM) that shift existing fragility curves appropriately to
15 consider nonlinear soil behavior and/or SSI. We apply our method to an exist-
16 ing block of -mainly- residential buildings in Thessaloniki, Greece. To derive
17 the fragility curves for the building block, we perform (i) incremental dynamic
18 analyses of the existing individual structures considering nonlinear soil be-
19 havior and SSI, (ii) incremental dynamic analyses for the existing structures
20 neglecting the underlying soil, (iii) fragility assessment using existing fragility
21 curves found in literature and (iv) fragility assessment using existing fragility
22 curves found in literature, but modified using our proposed FM to account for
23 nonlinear soil behavior and SSI. Next, assessment is also performed in terms of
24 vulnerability. A comparison between the obtained results highlights the effec-
25 tiveness of the proposed FM for large-scale risk assessment, and the necessity
26 to consider soil-related effects. In particular, the results are compared in terms
27 of fragility and vulnerability. Since the selection of the block is representative

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of the city center of Thessaloniki, our results will be indicative for city-level applications.

Keywords Vulnerability assessment · city-scale · fragility modifiers · BNWF

1 Introduction

Seismic protection of metropolitan areas with significant demographic and construction development, high population density, important economic, administrative, industrial, and residential buildings, extensive infrastructure and transport networks with various day-to-day activities requires the development of a reliable plan for addressing and mitigating the seismic risk. Particularly in the scenario where large sections of the population are affected, as well as human health and quality of life are threatened, priority is given to advanced methods for managing seismic risk. As a result of the many uncertainties involved in the elements at risk, the ability to determine seismic risk, complex vulnerability analysis, but also the level of damage and losses, seismic risk is undoubtedly extremely complicated.

In particular, several fragility and vulnerability functions have already been developed (Yepes-Estrada et al., 2016), covering a wide variety of structural typologies met worldwide and critical issues arise (Silva, 2017), depending on the use of seismic risk tools. Dabeek and Silva (2019) present an exposure model describing the residential building stock in the Middle East, developed for the purpose of multi-hazard risk assessment. Salgado-Gálvez et al. (2014) assess seismic risk for Medellín, the second-largest city of Colombia, exploiting spectral transfer functions for the seismic microzonation zones defined to include site amplification effects. Motamed et al. (2019) examine the residential, commercial and industrial building stock of Iran, providing fragility and vulnerability models using nonlinear time history analysis and ground motion records from the region. Silva et al. (2014b) based on existing studies and data from the 2011 Building Census in Portugal, move to assessing seismic risk at national level, while Sousa and Costa (2015) provide a comparison of risk levels between different epochs and Portuguese regions. Yepes et al. (2017) approach seismic risk at continental level, providing a transparent exposure model for the residential building stock in South America; Villar-Vega et al. (2017) fill the latter work with a uniform fragility model for the most representative building classes in the region, aiming at large-scale seismic risk. To a more considerable extent, Silva et al. (2020) provide a seismic risk overview at a global level. Additionally, (Silva et al., 2014a) developed OpenQuake, a tool to assess large-scale seismic risk, further applied combined with available data, e.g. the USGS ShakeMap system (Silva and Horspool, 2019).

Proportionately rare seismic events of great magnitude imply a lack of data regarding earthquake losses and damage, particularly when it comes to specific structural typologies, subsoil conditions and other particularities that further filter the available information. On the contrary, numerical models represent a nearly-always available means to assess earthquake risk. Still, subsoil-specific

71 studies of this extent are not available and soil-structure interaction (SSI)
72 effects are rarely incorporated (Rajeev and Tesfamariam, 2012; Karapetrou
73 et al., 2015; Tomeo et al., 2018; Petridis and Pitilakis, 2018, 2020; Karatzetzou
74 et al., 2020), consequently, generic fragility functions are usually adopted, only
75 parameterized in terms of the building typologies. SSI effects may contribute
76 either beneficially or detrimentally (Mylonakis and Gazetas, 2000; Karatzet-
77 zou and Pitilakis, 2018) to structural response and these effects are further
78 projected on the fragility and vulnerability assessment of the structure.

79 In this paper, we integrate nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects into
80 large-scale seismic risk assessment procedures. First, we assess seismic risk
81 for a block of buildings located in the center of Thessaloniki using explicit
82 nonlinear dynamic analyses. To provide a simplified and efficient tool for large-
83 scale purposes, we present and evaluate the concept of fragility modifiers (FM)
84 that account for SSI effects, directly applicable to existing fragility curves
85 (Petridis and Pitilakis, 2020). To ensure a direct and convenient scheme for
86 the application of our results –e.g. using OpenQuake (Silva et al., 2014a)– we
87 provide a set of fragility modifiers that appropriately change soil-independent
88 fragility curves found in the literature by multiplying their median values,
89 to account for nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects. Both analytical and
90 simplified FM approach outcomes are presented for the case of the city block in
91 the city center of Thessaloniki, highlighting the effectiveness of the latter, faster
92 and large-scale oriented approach. In particular, FM capture the differences
93 introduced by SSI effects in terms of vulnerability without the need for further
94 analyses, i.e., can be applied on top of any existing soil-independent fragility
95 curves.

96 **2 Methodology to derive the Fragility Modifiers**

97 The scope of this paper is to integrate nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects
98 into large-scale seismic risk assessment procedures. To do so, a wide set of FM
99 is used, facilitating rapid risk assessment without the need for explicit numer-
100 ical analyses. In this section, the methodology used to derive FM is briefly
101 presented. The reader is referred to Petridis and Pitilakis (2020) for a more
102 detailed description of the FM. The concept behind FM is to pre-calculate the
103 effects of SSI and/or site effects for different building typologies, soil profiles
104 and foundation types, thus having a ready-to-use set of coefficients that mod-
105 ify existing fragility curves. In essence, FM follow the use of existing fragility
106 curves that -by typology- enable risk analysts to assess seismic risk using pre-
107 defined curves without the need for further numerical analyses. Equivalently,
108 the use of FM enables risk analysts to include SSI effects using predefined
109 values, without running time-consuming elaborate numerical analyses.

110 The derivation of the FM begins with the definition of the building, the
111 foundation and the soil models. More specifically, one needs to discretize the
112 building in terms of the number of stories/height, the lateral load-resisting
113 structure and the distribution of the infills, as well as the regulations of the

114 corresponding seismic code. Then, the foundation type (footing, raft, etc.)
115 and the soil profiles (clay, sand, VS , among other parameters) are defined.
116 Next, soil-foundation compliance is modeled using appropriate elastic spring
117 and dashpot elements or nonlinear springs, and kinematic interaction is consid-
118 ered using closed-form equations. Since wave propagation is explicitly modeled
119 via numerical analyses of the soil models, all the ground motions considered in
120 this methodology must refer to bedrock conditions (soil type A in all seismic
121 codes). This ensures that any site effects and soil uncertainties are beforehand
122 absent. Incremental dynamic analysis is adopted as the analysis method to
123 derive clouds of PGA - maximum interstory drift pairs that are thereafter
124 post-processed to derive the corresponding fragility curves for a set of damage
125 states (DS). These steps are repeated two more times, assuming fixed-base
126 conditions; (i) fixed-base conditions *including* nonlinear soil behavior and site
127 effects and (ii) fixed-base conditions *neglecting* nonlinear soil behavior and
128 site effects, i.e. using the bedrock-level ground motions directly for the struc-
129 tural model analyses. In this manner, we obtain three different sets of fragility
130 curves, one set for the flexible-base case and two sets for the fixed-base, as de-
131 scribed. Finally, the ratios between the flexible-base and the fixed-base fragility
132 curves, regarding the PGA corresponding to 50% probability of exceeding a
133 damage state, provides the FM used here. Particular definitions and brief dis-
134 cussion of the separate steps is presented in the following subsections. The
135 reader is referred to Petridis and Pitilakis (2020) for a more detailed descrip-
136 tion and validation of the proposed methodology and the FM.

137 2.1 Buildings typologies

138 While the concept of FM may cover more or less any structural typology, here
139 we examine typical reinforced concrete buildings, designed and constructed
140 according to low seismic codes, resting on typical spread footings without
141 connecting beams. This is on purpose, since most historic city centers of the
142 southern European cities are built like that.

143 As indicative building typologies, we model reinforced concrete buildings
144 as described in Kappos et al. (2006). In particular:

- 145 – Regarding the lateral load resisting system, moment-resisting frames and
146 dual (frame+shear wall) buildings are analyzed.
- 147 – Regarding the height of the structures, low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise
148 models are examined.
- 149 – Regarding the infills, bare, regularly infilled and soft-story (pilotis) config-
150 urations are assumed.
- 151 – Regarding the seismic code, all the models are considered to be designed
152 and constructed following the provisions of the “Royal Decree of 1959,
153 Greece”, i.e. a low-code, nonductile behavior is expected.

154 For the numerical modeling we use OpenSEES (Mazzoni et al., 2009), includ-
155 ing the material nonlinearities associated via the application of the fiber ele-
156 ments provided. Standard, square-shaped footings are selected as the indicative

Table 1: Soil profiles investigated to derive FM

No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Vs (m/s)	>800	450	360	300	250	180	150
Type (EC8)	A	B	C	C	C	D	D

157 foundation type of the low-code structures studied, with typical dimensions
 158 verifying soil bearing capacity calculation.

159 2.2 Soil profiles and foundation modeling

160 All the examined building models are coupled with varying subsoil profiles to
 161 investigate the effects of both nonlinear soil behavior and SSI on the fragility
 162 and vulnerability curves. We select a non-symmetric array of soil models, pa-
 163 rameterized in terms of their shear wave velocity $V_{S,30}$, extending from rock
 164 to very soft soils, both for clay and for sand soil types. Based on the hypoth-
 165 esis that SSI is principally apparent on soft soil conditions, the set of soil
 166 profiles selected is soft-soil-skewed. Employing OpenSEES, each soil profile
 167 is formed as a pseudo-1D equivalent of the physical free-field to transfer the
 168 ground motion from the underlying bedrock to the surface. The “PressureIn-
 169 dependMultiYield” material is used to account for nonlinear soil behavior. The
 170 properties of the soil profiles define the beam-on-nonlinear-Winkler-foundation
 171 springs (BNWF) (Raychowdhury and Hutchinson, 2009; Harden and Hutchin-
 172 son, 2009; Gajan et al., 2010), applied to capture nonlinear SSI effects at the
 173 foundation level. Upon definition, these springs and dashpots are attached to
 174 the base of each footing to model the flexible-base response. **Structural founda-
 175 tion damage or soil-foundation plastification are not explicitly modeled, since
 176 the BNWF approach is only used to provide the nonlinear behavior of the
 177 springs adopted and thus, the relevant effects are not considered (Liu et al.,
 178 2013; Figini and Paolucci, 2017).** Table 1 presents the seven chosen soil profiles,
 179 classified according to EC8.

180 2.3 Dynamic analyses

181 Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) is run to obtain a cloud of intensity
 182 measure (IM) versus engineering demand parameter (EDP) pairs (Vamvatsikos
 183 and Cornell, 2002, 2004). We select PGA referring to the underlying bedrock
 184 as the IM and maximum interstory drift (maxISD) as the EDP. Selecting
 185 PGA on rock conditions as IM highlights the modification introduced by soil
 186 nonlinearity; the use of maxISD as the EDP provides an effective overview of
 187 the damage at global level. All of the input ground motions to the IDA are
 188 recorded on sites classified as rock, and scaled at bedrock level from 0.0 to 1.0
 189 g with a constant step of 0.05g.

190 2.4 Fragility modifiers (FM)

191 Fragility modifiers predefine the influence of SSI and local nonlinear site effects
 192 for different building, soil and foundation typologies. In essence, via analyzing
 193 different combinations, we obtain a set of FM that may subsequently be used
 194 on any relevant existing fragility curve found in literature. While a compre-
 195 hensive risk assessment procedure, including site amplification and foundation
 196 flexibility, is a feasible task for building-specific cases, the use of this method-
 197 ology for large-scale risk assessment studies at city-scale, is still cumbersome.
 198 To this end, we produce an assemblage of FM that appropriately shift existing
 199 fragility curves to incorporate nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects. Having
 200 derived the fragility curves for all the soil-building combinations, we evalu-
 201 ate the ratios between the PGAs associated with 50% probability of exceeding
 202 each damage state. This way, we estimate how much risk analysts have to shift
 203 the existing fixed-base fragility curve to approach the flexible-base one, with-
 204 out the need for additional numerical analyses. The inherent uncertainties are
 205 observed to be similar among the fixed- and flexible-base models. Therefore,
 206 we suggest a simple transpose of the fragility curves by multiplying the PGA
 207 at 50% probability of exceedance with the estimated FM, without altering
 208 the inclination of the curve, i.e. assuming that variability remains equal. In
 209 reality, the proposed FM are the outcome of this thorough procedure which es-
 210 timates the ratios between all studied instances (Petridis and Pitilakis, 2020).
 211 Equation 1 describes the calculation of the FM.

$$FM_i = \frac{PGA_{50\%,flexible-base,i}}{PGA_{50\%,fixed-base,i}} \quad (1)$$

212 in which, i loops over Slight Damage (SD), Moderate Damage (MD), Extensive
 213 Damage (ED) and Complete Damage (CD), $PGA_{50\%,flexible-base}$ is the peak
 214 ground acceleration at the underlying bedrock corresponding to 50% proba-
 215 bility of the flexible-base-on-soil model to exceed a given damage state i , and
 216 $PGA_{50\%,fixed-base}$ is its fixed-base counterpart.

217 3 The case study of Thessaloniki

218 To examine the influence of local site effects, nonlinear soil behavior and SSI
 219 on large-scale risk assessment and to evaluate the effectiveness of our FM
 220 approach, we select a block of 18 buildings located in the city center of Thes-
 221 saloniki as an illustrative case study. Thessaloniki, besides being the second
 222 largest city in Greece, is also the economic metropolis of Northern Greece,
 223 while being an important administrative, industrial, academic and cultural
 224 center. Its urban area is divided into 17 suburbs, the most important of which
 225 are in the municipality of Thessaloniki. Until just before the 20th century,
 226 the city maintained the structure of ancient times inside the Byzantine walls.
 227 However, in 1917 a devastating fire was the reason for the beginning of rebuild-
 228 ing. Specifically, 15000 buildings were erected in the decade between 1922 and

1932, 2200 of which are located in the city center and 3000 in the eastern part of Thessaloniki. In the 1970s, after the walls were demolished, the city's surface had practically doubled.

The city is located in the seismic zone of Axios, near the fault of the Serbian-Macedonian zone, one of the most seismotectonically active areas in Europe. The most recent worth-mentioning earthquake that hit Thessaloniki occurred in June 1978, with an epicenter 25 kilometers northeast of the city, 8 kilometers deep and $M=6.5$ ($IMM=VII-VIII$), resulting in the death of 45 people and many problems in the urban area.

The taxonomy of the building block under study was defined following a relevant survey (Riga et al., 2020), obtained from the Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) and more specifically the Population and Labor Market Statistics Department and the Census and Status Department. The census took place in 2011 and includes the building blocks of the Thessaloniki regional unit, which were classified by their respective geographical code and identification number. Initial classification was based on the number of dwellings inside each building block and more specifically follows subdivision into 0,1,2,3-5,6-9,10-19 and 20 or more apartments per block. The next distinction is made between exclusive and mixed-use buildings, with each classification broken down into more specific use categories. Finally, the building blocks are classified according to the type of the roof of the building and the main roofing material in: roofed buildings, roof tiles, roofing sheets or other materials. The criteria that guided the block selection for this study are:

- The block of buildings is located in the historic center of Thessaloniki.
- The soil on which the buildings are founded is type C according to EC8.
- Buildings are at a distance from the coastal front of Thessaloniki, to avoid liquefaction potential.
- Diversity in building typology, as the aim was to study both typical MRF and dual lateral load resisting systems.
- Variation in the number of floors and of the height of the buildings.
- The age of the buildings, since older structures form the majority of the city's historic center.
- Mostly residential use of the buildings were considered.

The building block #1858, as described in ELSTAT archives, is shown in Figure 1. This building block consists of ten buildings with an MRF system and eight with a dual system, whereas almost all of them were designed according to the seismic code of the Royal Decree of 1959 (RD'59) in Greece, while one is following the Additional Provisions of 1984 (AP'84).

3.1 Soil conditions

To achieve the accurate modeling of the soil layers, on which the structures under investigation are founded, borehole data were obtained from the microzonation study of Thessaloniki (Anastasiadis et al., 2001), labeled as region

Fig. 1: Thessaloniki city center map; zoomed map of the block examined and borehole locations.

Table 2: List of the buildings contained in the block examined

ID	Number of Stories	Structural Typology	Seismic Code	Area (m ²)
k1	5	MRF	RD'59	1200.00
k2	9	MRF	RD'59	1710.78
k3	5	DUAL	RD'59	1278.45
k4	8	DUAL	RD'59	2160.00
k5	9	MRF	RD'59	1300.00
k6	5	DUAL	RD'59	962.00
k7	9	MRF	RD'59	2160.00
k8	3	MRF	RD'59	864.00
k9	9	DUAL	RD'59	1710.78
k10	7	MRF	RD'59	1212.75
k11	9	DUAL	RD'59	1519.56
k12	6	MRF	RD'59	1596.48
k13	7	MRF	RD'59	1919.40
k14	8	DUAL	AP'84	1814.40
k15	6	MRF	RD'59	1666.65
k16	9	DUAL	RD'59	1944.00
k17	7	MRF	RD'59	2016.00
k18	10	DUAL	RD'59	3880.46

271 391 and 393. In particular, the location of the boreholes 391 and 393, as well
 272 as the location of the building block under investigation are shown in Figure 1.
 273 Data for each borehole includes the type of soil, its description, NSPT values
 274 and mass density. An essential variable required in the OpenSees soil models
 275 is the shear wave propagation velocity of each soil layer, for which equations
 276 2 and 3 from Pitilakis et al. (1992) are used, for sand and clay soil types,
 277 respectively:

$$V_s = 162.0 * N^{0.170} \quad (2)$$

Table 3: Borehole data, ID:391

UCS	Thickness (m)	Layer (m)	NSPT	Vs (m/s)	c (kPa)	$\phi()$	γ (kN/m ³)
GP	7	11.3	-	≤ 250.00	-	-	18.00
GP	4.3		-	250.00	-	-	16.00
ML	1.2	1.2	32.5	292.78	37	-	14.72
CL	1.5	1.5	16	259.55	37	-	14.72
SC	0.6	0.6	16	259.55	37	-	14.72
CL	4.9	7.9	28	285.45	37	-	14.72
CL	3		33.5	294.29	37	-	14.72
CL	4.5	4.5	79	340.50	37	-	14.72
CL	4.35	4.35	50	315.02	37	-	14.72

$$V_s = 165.7 * N^{0.190} \quad (3)$$

where N is the value of N_{SPT} . In all cases, mean values for medium dense sand and medium stiff clay were considered, i.e. $\phi=33^\circ$ and $c=37$ kPa. Layers with similar shear wave velocity values were considered as single homogeneous layers, with a total thickness equal to the sum of the thicknesses of the individual segments. In practice, this is a typical grouping procedure to avoid extreme fragmentation of the soil layers, a method also followed by geotechnical engineering practitioners. Table 3 and Table 4 present the details of each borehole and in particular, the type of soil layers, the thickness of each layer, the total drilling thickness, the value of N_{SPT} , the velocity of the shear waves within each soil layer, the cohesion, friction angle and the mass density.

4 Risk assessment approaches

We investigate different approaches to assess seismic risk in large-scale, mainly regarding the integration of local nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects. For this purpose, we compare fixed-base (FIX) and flexible-base (SSI) models. Site amplification and nonlinear soil response is taken into account (AMP). Fragility and vulnerability outcomes are derived either from nonlinear analyses (NLA) or from the literature, herein from Kappos et al. (2006) (K06) for the existing fragility curves and from Pitilakis et al. (2019) (P19) or EC8 (EN-1998) (EC8) for site amplification factors. FM are also used to embed SSI effects into existing reference fragility curves [REF(K06)] or applied on analytical curves [REF(NLA)]. Before the presentation of the approaches and the results, at building-specific or at block level, we provide a short description of the notation used in the forthcoming figures, as well as an visual diagram (Figure 2).

Table 4: Borehole data, ID:393

UCS	Thickness (m)	Layer (m)	NSPT	Vs (m/s)	c (kPa)	$\phi()$	γ (kN/m ³)
GP	9.5	9.5	-	≤ 250.00	-	-	18
SC	2.5	2.5	30	288.82	-	33	18.64
CL	2.5	9.0	49	313.94	37	-	14.72
CL	2.5		51	316.08	37	-	14.72
CL	4		56	321.15	37	-	14.72
CL	6.5	6.5	35.5	297.20	37	-	14.72
CL	10.5	42.7	50	315.02	37	-	14.72
CL	8		50	315.02	37	-	14.72
CL	8		50	315.02	37	-	14.72
CL	8		50	315.02	37	-	14.72
CL	8.2		50	315.02	37	-	14.72

Fig. 2: Description of the notation used.

- 302 – **SSI**: Describes the method to account for SSI effects.
- 303 – **NLA**: SSI inherently taken into account in the nonlinear analyses.
- 304 – **FM**: SSI is included via Fragility Modifiers.
- 305 – **FIX**: The structure is fixed-base, i.e. no SSI is included.
- 306 – **AMP**: Describes the method that accounts for site amplification.
- 307 – **NLA**: Site amplification is calculated via nonlinear dynamic analyses.
- 308 – **FM**: Site amplification via Fragility Modifiers.
- 309 – **EC8**: Site amplification using EC8 amplification factors.
- 310 – **P19**: Site amplification using the Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification
- 311 factors.
- 312 – **REF**: Describes the reference (fragility or vulnerability) curve.
- 313 – **NLA**: Reference (fragility or vulnerability) curve derived from analyses.
- 314 – **K06**: Reference (fragility or vulnerability) curve derived from Kappos
- 315 et al. (2006).

316 For example, [FIX|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)] is a composite acronym for the case
317 of a fixed-base structure "FIX" resting on soil profile where site amplification
318 "AMP" is calculated based on the Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification factors
319 "P19" applied on the reference "REF" curve of Kappos et al. (2006) "K06". In
320 all cases, PGA refers to the acceleration recorded at the bedrock, to ease compar-
321 isons and liaison with seismic hazard analyses. Wherever site amplification
322 effects are included, PGA still refers to bedrock level, however the probability
323 of exceedance or losses corresponds to the amplified ground motion, i.e. site
324 amplification effects are inherent in the curve. Repair cost and economic data
325 are based on Kappos et al. (2006).

326 4.1 Numerical analyses

327 Numerical analysis of all the the buildings that form the building block is the
328 most accurate -yet time-consuming- approach to assess seismic vulnerability.
329 Here, this method is considered a benchmark to evaluate the effectiveness of
330 the approaches that follow. To facilitate the modeling process of the buildings,
331 the architectural drawings and formwork of the buildings from the Depart-
332 ment of Construction and Urban Planning of the Municipality of Thessaloniki
333 were acquired, as well as from the Directorate of Civil Engineering. Nonlinear
334 soil behavior is explicitly taken into account via pseudo-1D soil models that
335 transfer the ground motion from the bedrock to the surface of the soil domain.
336 To use the beam-on-nonlinear-Winkler-foundation (BNWF) modeling, all the
337 buildings of the building block were modeled as 2D equivalent frames in both
338 directions.

339 For the cases where information about structural detailing was missing, the
340 specifications of Kappos et al. (2006) on the geometry and reinforcement of
341 typical building structures were used. This procedure was also completed by an
342 on-site visit and rapid survey. According to the architectural and structural
343 blueprints, all the buildings were categorized as either MRF or dual, with
344 respect to their lateral load resisting system.

Fig. 4: Fragility curves (top) and vulnerability curves (bottom) derived from the nonlinear IDA performed for the building k6, for all damage states (SD, MD, ED and CD). We compare the fixed-base model neglecting any soil effects [FIX(NLA)] with the fixed-base model including nonlinear soil behavior in terms of site amplification [FIX(NLA)|AMP(NLA)] and the flexible-base model including nonlinear soil behavior in terms of site amplification [SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)].

Fig. 5: Vulnerability curves derived for the building k1 from the nonlinear IDA [FIX(NLA), FIX(NLA)|AMP(NLA), SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)], compared with the Kappos et al. (2006) existing curves, modified to include site amplification effects using Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification factors [FIX|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)].

nerability curves at building block level. EC8 provides soil-dependent values, ignoring the level of seismic intensity, while Pitilakis et al. (2019) further refine amplification with respect to different seismic intensities.

Following the introduced notation in Figure 2, the use of existing fragility curves including site amplification produces fixed-base [FIX] curves, including site amplification effects using either Pitilakis et al. (2019) [AMP(P19)] or EC8 [AMP(EC8)] amplification factors, upon a reference curve, either derived from literature (here, Kappos et al. (2006) [REF(K06)]) or using the fixed-base on rock curve from the analyses (REF(NLA)). Figure 5 shows the vulnerability curves derived for the building k1 from nonlinear IDA, compared with the Kappos et al. (2006) vulnerability curves, modified to include site amplification effects using the Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification factors.

Comparing loss curves derived from nonlinear IDA with the one from literature data (Kappos et al., 2006; Pitilakis et al., 2019), as shown in Figure 5, we observe that the latter approach captures the additional losses introduced by soil-related effects for PGA at rock greater than 3m/s^2 . In specific, for PGA values (X-axis) greater than 3.0m/s^2 , [FIX|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)] curve almost matches [SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)] curve. However, SSI effects are still neglected using this approach. For building-level purposes, reasonable matching of the analytical curves is achieved using literature data, for the majority of the buildings studied here. On the contrary, SSI effects -from a vulnerability point of view- are more influential for lower damage states and lower PGA (Petridis and Pitilakis, 2020), thus with this approach we fail to capture addi-

397 tional loss for low PGA. Also, PGA at bedrock around $1\text{-}3\text{m/s}^2$ is commonly
398 used in seismic risk scenarios, and consequently, an accurate approximation of
399 the accompanying losses is essential.

400 4.3 Existing fragility curves, SSI-only FM & site amplification

401 Extending current approaches to including SSI effects, we use a wide set of
402 FM that account for SSI influence on existing fragility curves. Parameterized
403 in terms of structural typologies, soil conditions, and damage levels, the FM
404 approach offers a fast alternative to include the latter effects in large-scale risk
405 assessment. SSI-only FM are easily combined with existing site amplification
406 factors to modify existing fragility curves and estimate seismic vulnerability
407 and risk. In this study, we employ SSI-only FM (Petridis and Pitilakis, 2020)
408 combined with the EC8 and the Pitilakis et al. (2019) site amplification factors
409 to estimate building block vulnerability. The results are compared with the
410 numerical approach to determine the effectiveness of this simplified approach.

411 Following the notation introduced above, the use of existing fragility curves
412 including site amplification and SSI effects via FM produces flexible-base
413 [SSI(FM)] curves, including site amplification effects using either Pitilakis et al.
414 (2019) [AMP(P19)] or EC8 [AMP(EC8)] amplification factors, accounted on
415 top of a reference curve derived either from literature (here, Kappos et al.
416 (2006)) [REF(K06)] or using the fixed-base-on-rock curve from the analyses
417 (REF(NLA)). $\text{FM}_{V_s=250}$ indicates that the springs used to model foundation
418 flexibility are estimated assuming shear wave velocity of the homogenized un-
419 derlying soil layer equal to 250m/s , while $\text{FM}_{V_s=180}$ stands for shear wave
420 velocity of the homogenized underlying soil layer equal to 180m/s . The reason
421 behind this parametric approach is that the top soil layer below this building
422 block #1858 consists mainly of low quality soil materials, which may corre-
423 spond to a shear wave velocity less than 200m/s . Figure 6 presents the vul-
424 nerability curves derived for the building k8 from nonlinear IDA including
425 site amplification and SSI effects, compared to the fixed-base Kappos et al.
426 (2006) existing curves modified to include only site amplification effects using
427 Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification factors, and also compared to the Kappos
428 et al. (2006) existing curves, modified again to include both site amplification
429 and SSI effects, using the Pitilakis et al. (2019) soil amplification factors and
430 our FM (respectively).

431 Comparing the loss curve derived from nonlinear IDA with the ones con-
432 structed using literature data (Kappos et al., 2006; Pitilakis et al., 2019) and
433 the corresponding FM, as shown in Figure 6, we observe that FM provide
434 the additional losses expected, with respect to the analytical curve. However,
435 the $\text{FM}_{V_s=180}$ tend to overestimate the expected losses. On the other hand,
436 $\text{FM}_{V_s=250}$, which correspond to a more realistic average value of the under-
437 lying layers' shear wave velocities, provides the most accurate approximation
438 of the analytical curve, among the approaches presented, with respect to the
439 reference case by elaborate numerical analyses [SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)].

Fig. 6: Vulnerability curves derived for the building k8 from nonlinear IDA, including site amplification and SSI effects [SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)], compared with Kappos et al. (2006) existing curves, modified only to include site amplification effects using Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification factors [FIX|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)], and also compared with Kappos et al. (2006) existing curves, modified to include both site amplification and SSI effects using Pitilakis et al. (2019) amplification factors and our FM, respectively [SSI(FM_{V_s=250})|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)] and [SSI(FM_{V_s=180})|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)].

440 5 Block-level seismic vulnerability

441 Integrating nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects into building-level fragility
 442 curves is a feasible task, either performed via numerical analyses or using
 443 literature data. However, integrating these effects into large-scale assessment
 444 procedures is almost impossible via the numerical method. In this context,
 445 the concept of FM is used and its effectiveness is tested in this section. The
 446 advantage of the latter method is the direct applicability without the need for
 447 further numerical analyses.

448 Adding the individual vulnerability curves, we obtain an overview of the
 449 expected losses at city-block level. The influence of both nonlinear soil behavior
 450 and SSI adds up to a substantial degree, either defined as loss ratio or repair
 451 cost. At the building block level, where all structures are now involved, the
 452 economic losses resulting from nonlinear soil behavior are more significant than
 453 those arising from soil-structure interaction. It is worth noting that buildings
 454 presenting the most economic losses are not necessarily the most vulnerable in
 455 terms of their structural response, as the losses occur depending on the built
 456 area. Consequently, less structural damage may sometimes lead to greater
 457 economic losses for buildings with large built areas. Figure 7 presents the
 458 block-level vulnerability for all the different assessment approaches.

Fig. 7: Vulnerability curves at block level, i.e. sum of the individual building-level curves for the different approaches adopted. We compare the curves derived from the nonlinear IDA performed [FIX(NLA), SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA), FIX(NLA)|AMP(NLA)] (i) with Kappos et al. (2006) existing curves, modified to include site amplification and SSI effects using Pitilakis et al. (2019) and (ii) EC8 amplification factors and our FM, respectively [SSI(FM $_{V_s=250}$)|AMP(P19)|REF(K06), SSI(FM $_{V_s=250}$)|AMP(EC8)|REF(K06) and SSI(FM $_{V_s=180}$)|AMP(P19)|REF(K06)], (iii) with the Kappos et al. (2006) existing curves, modified to include site amplification effects using Pitilakis et al. (2019) and (iv) EC8 amplification factors [FIX|AMP(P19)|REF(K06) and FIX|AMP(EC8)|REF(K06)], and (v) finally with Kappos et al. (2006) existing curves, neglecting any soil influence.

459 In general, nonlinear soil behavior and SSI increase the losses expected under
 460 the different seismic scenarios. Site amplification influences the outcome
 461 of the assessment to a large extent, while SSI influence is milder, yet significant,
 462 as seen in the block-level results. Nonlinear soil behavior, in the sense of
 463 ground motion amplification, increases the expected repair cost of the block
 464 by about 2M€, or slightly more along the vulnerability curves. Indicatively,
 465 SSI alone increases the expected repair cost of the block by about 1M€, or
 466 even more along the vulnerability curves.

467 To present an efficient method to include SSI effects in large-scale risk
 468 assessment procedures, we validate the applicability of our FM approach by
 469 comparing the modified vulnerability (using the FM approach) with the vul-
 470 nerability curves derived from the nonlinear dynamic analyses. As shown in
 471 Figure 7 there is a significant difference between the "reference" fixed-base-on-
 472 rock curves, i.e. the one aggregated from the analyses and the one aggregated
 473 from literature (Kappos et al., 2006). This means that the starting point, upon
 474 which nonlinear soil behavior and SSI are evaluated differs significantly. On
 475 the other hand, the FM approach seems to capture similar difference -in terms
 476 of additional repair cost- between the fixed-base curve and the SSI-inclusive

Fig. 8: Vulnerability curves at block level, i.e. sum of the individual building-level curves for the different approaches adopted. We compare the curves derived from the performed nonlinear IDA [FIX(NLA), SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)] with the fixed-base reference curves derived from the nonlinear IDA [FIX(NLA)], modified to include site amplification and SSI effects using Pitilakis et al. (2019) and EC8 amplification factors and our FM, respectively [SSI(FM_{V_s=250})|AMP(P19)|REF(NLA), SSI(FM_{V_s=250})|AMP(EC8)|REF(NLA) and SSI(FM_{V_s=180})|AMP(P19)|REF(NLA)].

477 one. To further illustrate the effectiveness of this approach, we apply the FM
 478 approach on the fixed-base curve derived from the analyses (and not from the
 479 literature). In this way, we adopt a common starting point to evaluate SSI
 480 effects. Figure 8 presents the block-level vulnerability, calculated using the
 481 fixed-base-on-rock fragility curves derived from the numerical analyses as refer-
 482 ence, and then applying the FM on those reference curves. As seen in Figure
 483 8, the numerical block-level vulnerability curve is effectively approached by
 484 the three curves that result from the application of the FM on the numerical
 485 fixed-base reference curve, including site amplification effects by use of either
 486 Pitilakis et al. (2019) or EC8 amplification factors.

487 In addition, the response of each building to the addressed cases mentioned
 488 above is further illustrated for the seismic hazard scenario of PGA at rock equal
 489 to 0.16g. Under this seismic excitation the expected spatial distribution of the
 490 central loss index of each structure is shown in Figure 9, with the following
 491 discretization:

- 492 – Blue: 0-0.10 level at which construction is moderately damaged
- 493 – Green: 0.10-0.30 level during which construction sustains major damage
- 494 – Orange: 0.30-0.60 level at which construction is subject to severe damage
 495 and
- 496 – Red: 0.60-1.00, which represents the potential collapse of the structure.

Fig. 9: Distribution of the central loss index at the block, as derived from the nonlinear IDA. Loss is estimated as the ratio between repair cost and replacement cost (build new). From left to right: fixed-base approach neglecting any soil effects [FIX(NLA)], fixed-base approach including nonlinear soil behavior in terms of site amplification [FIX(NLA)|AMP(NLA)], and flexible-base approach including nonlinear soil behavior in terms of site amplification [SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)].

Fig. 10: Expected spatial distribution of the repair costs (M €) of the structures, as derived from the nonlinear IDA. From left to right: fixed-base approach neglecting any soil effects [FIX(NLA)], fixed-base approach including nonlinear soil behavior in terms of site amplification [FIX(NLA)|AMP(NLA)], and flexible-base approach including nonlinear soil behavior in terms of site amplification [SSI(NLA)|AMP(NLA)].

497 Loss is estimated as the ratio between repair cost and replacement cost (build
498 new).

499 The same procedure is carried out for the expected spatial distribution of
500 the repair costs (M €) of the structures under the impact of the seismic scenario
501 with $PGA=0.16g$ for the different soil-foundation models. The results are
502 aggregated for the worst-response direction. Figure 10 presents the expected
503 spatial distribution of the repair costs (M €) of the structures.

504 As seen for this selected scenario, both site amplification and SSI increase
505 the expected losses. Figure 9 and Figure 10 provide an indicative picture of the
506 damage and cost distribution at a larger scale. Extrapolation of the additional
507 losses due to soil-related effects from building and block level to urban scale
508 highlights the necessity for the integration of nonlinear soil behavior and SSI
509 effects into seismic risk assessment.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we discuss the necessity, the feasibility and the applicability of different approaches to integrate nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects into large-scale seismic risk assessment. The influence of soil-related effects is evaluated and the fast, simplified method of fragility modifiers (FM) (presented elsewhere (Petridis and Pitilakis, 2020)) is briefly presented, with respect to large-scale risk assessment procedures.

Nonlinear soil behavior and SSI alter the vulnerability of the examined buildings, increasing the expected losses for the majority of the studied cases. Site amplification triggered by soft soil media above the bedrock increases vulnerability to a significant extent, while SSI influences the outcome, but to a milder degree. Moving from building to block level, additive losses due to the latter effects further alter seismic risk, highlighting the need for an accurate and simplified method to include soil-related effects in large-scale risk assessment. Besides, we analyze a block of buildings in the historic center of the city of Thessaloniki, Greece, and we observe that the simplified FM approach provides an effective alternative to full numerical modeling of vulnerability, complemented by site amplification factors readily found in literature.

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